

MATLAB main code- Simultaneous analysis of $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ and contraction on isolated smooth muscle cells

This code calculates the $[Ca^{2+}]_i$ and cell length on a sequence of images stored in a multidimensional array (3-D array) multi-Tiff format file (*.tiff). As note, the green text indicates a comment.

[The code starts here.](#)

[Image segmentation analysis to identify the cell area from the background area using a threshold of one standard deviation.](#)

```
[H, W, NFrames] = size(Images); % H, pixel Height size. W, pixel Width size. NFrames,  
number of images in the sequence.  
[MeanI,Cell_Region] = CellArea(Images, H, W, NFrames);% Image is a 3-D array where  
the image sequence is stored.
```

[Calculate \$\[Ca^{2+}\]_i\$](#)

```
[CellSubsB]=Fluor_one_cell(Images, NFrames, Cell_Region, H,W);% Calculate mean  $[Ca^{2+}]_i$   
and performed background subtraction  
SampleRate=2;%Time in Seconds  
TotalTime=SampleRate* NFrames;% Total time in seconds  
time=linspace(0,TotalTime, NFrames);%In seconds
```

[Calculate cell length.](#)

```
[Total_objects,LENGTH_CELL, Obj_M,Object_num]=Skeleton_cell(Images, NFrames, H,  
W);%Calculate length cell in microns
```

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